

A HISTORY OF PREJUDICE: SEXUAL HARASSMENT & ABUSE OF DOMESTIC WORKERS DURING COVID -19

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 has affected a wide range of people, but the risk and consequences of contracting the virus have not been evenly known: workers in the informal economy have been disproportionately affected. Economic support and protective equipment provided by governments and employers to formal economy workers have not consistently reached those in the informal economy. Many had to (attempt to) continue to work in unsafe conditions. Evictions, police brutality and confiscation against informal traders and market vendors. The pandemic has had a gendered impact on women in informal employment, particularly due to their significant representation in care and domestic work. COVID-19 also exacerbated sexual and gender-based violence against women migrant workers' in irregular situations. The perpetrators who are aware of this group is unlikely to report the violence, due to their specific experiences of discrimination and fear of arrest or deportation.

Keywords: Sexual harassment, Domestic Workers, Informal Economy, Pandemic Situation

INTRODUCTION

The ILO (The International Labour Organization) defines domestic work as “work performed in or for a household or households”. A domestic worker is “any person engaged in domestic work within an employment relationship”, excluding those who perform domestic work only occasionally or sporadically and not on an occupational basis”. Almost 75% of domestic workers globally were estimated by the ILO to be in informal employment in 2013 (50 million out of 67 million) (King-Dejardin, 2016). Estimates are that the number of domestic workers worldwide more than doubled between the 1990s and 2013, rising from 33 million to 67.1 million (WIEGO). Reasons behind this growth include the increase of women working outside the home, a decline in the public provision of care services and reduction of the support previously provided by extended family (International Labour Office, 2015). Domestic workers are overwhelmingly female (80%) and concentrated in cleaning and care services. Men generally gain higher pay in

occupations in domestic employment in which they predominate, for example, as gardeners, drivers, or security guards.

There are 11.8 million Women with disabilities which were domestic workers in India who experience considerable difficulties in the everyday lives. With high poverty levels, poor health conditions, lower incomes, lower education and a patriarchal system, they face further dangers in COVID-19. To take up the challenge immediate steps would have to be taken in the context of food and medicines. It was soon realized that some women were getting left out as information by governments which had universal reach, was not accessible. There was, thus, strong fear that women would be affected by the novel coronavirus and not be able to reach medical help and access treatment.

Recent years have seen the emergence of gig-based domestic work (ODI, 2016) where workers are engaged “on demand” via e-platforms. There is potential for employers to shop around for the cheapest workers whenever they need it. This type of fragmentation and gig-based approach together has been called the “Urbanisation” of domestic work. It poses challenges in organising and can heighten the burden of risk carried by the workers and lessen the risk to employers.

Despite being called “the work that makes possible all other work” (Poo, 2019), domestic work is not regarded by many as “real” work and remains undervalued and underpaid. The association of femininity, hence women, with the private sphere of the home and with the work that occurs in it results from the unpaid reproductive and caring roles women have been assigned and have performed in the house and the family across space and throughout history (Zhen, 1907). Domestic work in the homes of others is generally performed by disadvantaged women from lower socio-economic positions and racial or ethnic groups or castes with little or no access to education, in systems with class inequalities (Ribeiro Corossacz, 2019).

In countries with a history of colonialism, domestic work is often carried out by black or indigenous women or by women from the lowest castes and class. In America, for example, domestic work has roots in the legacy of slavery and colonialism. For centuries, it was performed by black enslaved women, who were routinely and legally permitted to be sexually violated by white male “owners” (Poo, 2018). In wealthy countries, domestic work is often carried out by women migrant workers, forming the global care chain by moving from poorer to wealthier states. They tend to leave their own families and homes in the global south to care for those in countries that are historically colonised. Racial inequalities that structure social hierarchies in the latter, marginalise these workers and deny them the enjoyment of their rights (Benería, et.al., 2012).

Another gross violation concerning women informal sector workers is sexual harassment at the workplace. The matter is commonplace yet invisible because of the nature of work and their workplaces. Safe working environment is something that is

missing at many informal workspaces. Cases of sexual abuse and harassment at the workplace has not received enough mainstream social attention or put to legal scrutiny. The incidences of sexual harassment of women workers in workplaces, such as construction sites, informal vendor markets, domestic workers at residences, agricultural fields and small-sized factories, go mostly unnoticed. The available legal provisions protecting some of the women workers in the informal sector are the Building and Other Construction Workers (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1996, The Inter-State Migrant Workmen (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1979, The Unorganized Workers' Social Security Act, 2008.

Research has thoroughly documented the human rights violations and the verbal, psychological, physical and sexual violence to which domestic workers are routinely the subject without relief. These include: sexual abuse, exploitation and harassment, trafficking, forced labour, imprisonment in the employer's house, control of food consumption, wage theft, non-payment of health care in cases of work accidents, absence of maternity leave, psychological coercion and extortion (Figueiredo, et.al., 2018) Workers and live-in domestic workers are the most vulnerable as the risk of deportation limits their ability and willingness to seek help. Undocumented migrant women choose domestic work in part because they associate private spaces with lower risk of being found by authorities compared to a factory or other less secluded workplaces, yet they bring other dangers. Immigrant domestic workers face challenges in escaping abusive households, as exemplified by the story of a Mexican victim-survivor working for a chiropractor in the USA: "She was afraid that the doctor would kill her (and no one would even notice she was missing); she had no money, identification, or knowledge of English; she did not think that the police would believe her word against that of a doctor; and she felt that she would be blamed." (Vellos, 1997).

A HISTORY OF PREJUDICE

The vulnerability of domestic workers that has come to light during this lockdown in fact has a long history. This sector remains deeply steeped in a culture of servitude across South Asia, rather than employment of a contractual nature.

Most jobs that entail domestic work do not in practice involve formal employment contracts. This essentially leaves domestic workers outside the sphere of most regulatory frameworks of the sort that govern the organised sector. The 2008, Unorganised Workers Social Security Act which was intended to provide welfare and social security to unorganised workers has been found insufficient in terms of design, government implementation, and so on.

Currently, regulation is from the perspective of monitoring the domestic worker—such as police verification—and not necessarily to guarantee the workers his/her rights and protections. Some may be in possession of Aadhar Cards, but there is no clear

data available on whether this is a significant number. A section of this workforce is migrants who moved from rural to urban areas in search of employment; some may be entirely undocumented. A majority live in rented premises without court registered leases, and thus lack valid residence proof, which is crucial for the issuance of almost every identity document, including ration cards.

Domestic work takes place in an unconventional setting, i.e. the household, unlike most other forms of labour market activities. Thus, the implementation of legalities that otherwise inform any kind of contractual employment poses an additional challenge. As a result, domestic workers often have to rely on the generosity of the employer. These circumstances can directly or indirectly, make them vulnerable to poor working conditions, extended work hours, lack of job security, sexual or physical abuse, etc.

Another serious challenge for the promotion and protection of domestic worker rights is the historic and economic devaluation of their work. Simply domestic work is not viewed as ‘real’ work. Instead, it is largely perceived as an extension of household chores that are not accounted for as contributors to a country’s economic growth.

Domestic workers have always been in a uniquely disadvantaged position in India, and South Asia. They continue to face hardships stemming not only from the informal nature of their employment, but the cultural prejudice towards this kind of work, and the subservience expected of those who undertake it. These issues predate COVID-19—the lockdown guidelines only served to exacerbate them, and bring them into greater focus. But, while there may be no villain in this specific case, there is a clear victim.

AMBIGUOUS GUIDELINES

In the lockdown period, anecdotal evidence reveals that many domestic workers have been abruptly dismissed, received pay cuts, have faced harassment or eviction from their rented accommodation due to the inability to pay rent, and have subsequently lost their livelihood sustenance.

However, even with the lockdown, relaxations on physical movement now underway; many domestic workers continue to confront an uncertain future. This is largely because the lockdown guidelines issued by the central government did not clearly mention whether domestic workers could resume work or did they disallow it explicitly.

Admittedly, the government's focus—at both the central and state levels—is, as it ought to be, on containing the spread of the virus, and addressing the severity of a crisis that has been compounded by resource scarcity. They are not expected to outline all specificities, and in a federal structure such as India's decision-making on secondary issues, in this, case domestic work, must be delegated. At the same time, it is important to

acknowledge that it is precisely this lack of clarity that disproportionately disadvantages domestic workers. The guidance that anything not explicitly prohibited can be considered permissible leaves too much room for interpretation by local authorities to undertake their own measures.

As a result of the ambiguity, Residents Welfare Associations (RWAs) in several cities have been undertaking their own decisions regarding resumption of work for domestic workers. This pandemic is a unique situation, and once again, most of these RWAs are prioritising their own personal safety. They are acting within their right to interpret the guidelines as per their understanding. However, this can't be said that all their measures are reasonable, in keeping with governmental guidance.

Some RWAs have imposed a ban on the entry of domestic workers into their localities even if all precautionary protocols are being followed. Others are allowing only those domestic workers travelling from green zones. In some cases, domestic workers are not allowed in the house unless they have downloaded the Aarogya Setu app in their phones, which fails to take cognisance of the fact that those currently not even making daily wages can ill-afford to purchase or own smart phones.

SEXUAL HARASSMENT OF DOMESTIC WORKERS

Many studies have documented widespread sexual harassment of domestic workers (Ribeiro Corossacz, 2019; DeSouza, 2009; Velloso, 1997; Figueiredo, et. al., 2018).

A 2018 survey conducted in India of 291 domestic workers found that over 29% of them experienced sexual harassment at work: 19% ignored the incident, 15% spoke with their friends about it, and 20% of them complained to the police, without results (The New Indian Express, 2018).

It has been argued that sexual harassment of domestic workers is used as a tool “to inscribe shame onto the workers’ bodies to justify their exploitation” (Saldaña - Tejada, 2014). Sexual harassment in most cases is perpetrated by male employers and younger male members of the house. Female employers also accuse the worker of instigating the behaviour and retaliate against them (Vox, 2018). While generally it proves difficult to challenge a perpetrator of sexual harassment directly, for some migrant domestic workers it may also be completely at odds with cultural norms that mitigate against confronting men (Velloso, 1997). Domestic workers have described their work as a journey to find the right jobs in good homes where they can work safely, by learning how to identify potential aggressors (Saldaña-Tejada, 2014). The informal nature of domestic work contributes to perpetrators seeing such workers as ideal targets for sexual harassment.

Domestic work is conducive to sexual harassment in part because of the privacy of the workplace. Work is conducted in isolation and behind closed doors. Private households are not universally considered to be workplaces, contrary to international standards. This is the reason why domestic work is largely informal and the employers are unwilling to declare the employment status of those workers to social security departments (Figueiredo, et. al., 2018). Workplaces that employ a number of staff often have codes of conduct that can be applied to all, at least in theory; this is not so for domestic workers, not are there human resource colleagues, welfare staff – any third person to whom workers can turn if they are targeted for sexual harassment. Verbal agreements create job insecurity and enable employers to dismiss workers at any time.

The relationship between domestic workers and their employers is generally characterised by subordination, power inequalities, as well as proximity and direct dependency of the worker on the employer. These factors enable sexual harassment perpetrators to feel confident of an absence of risk of accountability and may cause confusion for the workers on whether compliance with sexual demands are an inevitable part of their job as domestic workers (Ip, Fish, 2020).

Domestic workers tend to be poorly paid and unlikely to have no significant savings. So, they are highly dependent on income which is earned from the domestic work to cover basic needs (Gallotti, 2015). They are likely to have financial insecurities which force them to depend on works. They are scattered across households, making connections and networking difficult: sharing information or supporting each other and organising is challenging. Migrant domestic workers with irregular terms of engagement are more likely than others to continue working for abusive employers, due to fear of being reported by the employers.

The dangers of sexual harassment can vary between ‘live-in’ and ‘live-out’ domestic workers, and between local and migrant domestic workers. ‘Live-in’ domestic workers’ risk of sexual harassment is constantly increasing. They are dependent on their employers for accommodation, which can often lack privacy, they have little freedom or mobility (in some situations and in certain regions, there are no days off work) and some are prohibited from using phones (Ip, Fish, 2020). These factors reduce their ability to build a social network which is important for the support it can provide, and this situation restricts their ability to make reports.

COVID – 19 AND SEXUAL HARASSMENT OF DOMESTIC WORKERS:

The COVID -19 pandemic affected domestic work with the ILO estimating that in June 2020, over 55 of 67 million (75%) domestic workers were at significant risk of losing their jobs due to lockdowns and no or poor social security coverage.

While there is no yet statistical data available on sexual harassment of domestic workers during the pandemic, accounts provided by domestic workers' organisations indicate that sexual harassment unsurprisingly did not stop during this time and that fear of job losses inhibited their responses. During the lockdown, it has been observed that the 'live-in' domestic workers confined with their employer who may also be the perpetrators of sexual harassment. Past epidemics such as Ebola evidenced that women and girls, including migrants, were at heightened risk of gender-based violence and of sexual exploitation and abuse, a pattern that may well be mirrored in the 2020 pandemic.

RECOMMENDATIONS CONCERNING SEXUAL HARASSMENT IN DOMESTIC WORK

- States to develop mass public campaigns on sexual harassment to include the specifics of domestic work and the private household. Such campaigns to be developed with the guidance and support of domestic workers organisations.
- Women domestic workers' organisations and NGOs shall develop and offer training on sexual harassment that upholds UN Women's standards open to all domestic workers, including those in informal employment and not affiliated to workers' organisations.
- Extend legal protection from sexual harassment in the world of work to all farm workers, including those in informal and non-standard (casual, short term, seasonal) employment.
- Ensure legal avenues of entry through immigration for agricultural workers to perform seasonal and temporary labour and ensure these workers have equal protections to others.
- Ensure undocumented migrant farm workers have legal and social protections.
- Reinforce labour inspections in farms, fields and plantations, and ensure that they include monitoring of sex discrimination, including sexual harassment.

Further, the issues of violence and harassment at the workplace has taken a new dimension altogether during the crisis, which calls upon governments to revisit the existing legislative mechanism and develop adequate response mechanisms for addressing

new forms of harassment that affect workers well-being. The international labour standards can provide guidelines for informed policy action in this direction. There is also a need to develop gender-sensitive social protection policies for protecting the rights of women workers in the informal sector.

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